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Market-based procurement of grid-friendly flexibility – the ENFLATE project

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Abstract

ENFALTE is an international research consortium funded within the Horizon Europe framework [1]. Aim is to support the electrification of the heat and mobility sector by developing tools for the streamlined integration of intermittent renewable energy sources at large scales. Thereby, flexibility procurement and coordination platforms are being developed and field tested. In total, six demonstration sites are deployed in Bulgaria, Greece, Spain, Sweden, and Switzerland. Among the consortium partners are prosumers, distribution system operators, transmission system operators, market operators, aggregators, regulatory bodies, flexibility service providers, and manufacturers.

This contribution outlines the intermediate results related to the eastern Switzerland demonstrator after one third of the overall project duration. Focus lies on the market design and its adaption into the EPEX SPOT “localflex” market platform. The platform covers the end-to-end journey for market-based flexibility procurement, from onboarding and asset registration, through trading, to calculating baselining and settlement results after flexibility events. A grid model within the platform represents the distribution substations where the local distribution operator requires flexibility. Assets are then associated with the correct substation and can be used to provide localized flexibility or aggregated to offer flexibility at higher voltage levels for the balancing group and TSO. Transactions on localflex are conducted by matching buy and sell orders via closed-gate, pay-as-clear auctions, after an accumulation period during which orders are submitted on the localflex platform.

The proposed market design will accelerate the coordination of TSOs, DSOs and consumers, by enabling the access of distribution grid-connected assets in flexibility markets, and thereby lower the barriers for the small-scale assets’ introduction in flexibility markets towards a robust pan-European electricity network that optimally operates with a 100% RES penetration rate while being economically viable for long-term operation.

Introduction

Today, only large assets participate in European flexibility markets, failing to address growing issues in local distribution networks and excluding the flexibility potential of a large portion of smaller installations. In Europe, demand side flexibility (DSF) is recognized as an instrument for the best utilization of current distribution grids and consequently to the best allocation of resources for grid investments. However, as of today, the number of local flexibility markets in the EU is limited to a small number of projects, most of which are in pilot stage.

This contribution outlines how a digital marketplace can lower the barriers for smaller assets to deliver flexible power at the distribution level. This will be achieved through standardization of the market process, digitization of the operation and harmonization into a local flexibility mechanism. Through the demonstration activities it is expected to diminish the costs associated with market-based procurement of flexibility in comparison to traditional approaches of flexibility activation (e.g. ripple control). At the same time, the hosting capacity of the grid shall be increased due to flexibility being used to avoid curtailment of renewable energy and the MV transformer lifespan will be improved due to improved utilization factor and reduced peak load.

1. Project Background and Implementation

This demonstration project achieves flexibility for grid resilience through consumer involvement and distributed energy resources integration via local flexibility markets. A centralized market platform facilitates the coordination of demand side flexibility contracting and activation. On the seller side of the market, flexibility offers from residential heat pumps, electric boilers and electric car charging are submitted to the market via an aggregator. On the buyer side, multiple actors purchase flexibility for a variety of use cases: (1.) The balancing group may purchase flexibility from the local market to optimize its day-ahead profile on the energy-only market. (2.) Closer to real time, demand side flexibility facilitates the avoidance of balancing group imbalance costs. (3.) The TSO procures short-term flexibility related to balancing services. In the pilot, this use case is facilitated via an aggregator. (4.) The local distribution system operator uses flexibility for peak shaving. The peak loading of grid components reduces, and costly grid expansion measures are postponed. During such hours of critically high energy flows, the physical grid limits are incorporated into the boundary conditions of the market clearing optimization algorithm.

Figure 1: Market actors and their data interactions

For the trials, the platform has been configured to run utilization (activation) auctions at the day-ahead stage and then intraday on an hourly basis. Intraday auctions are scheduled to run 45 minutes before delivery to best facilitate the various use cases of flexibility procurement being demonstrated.

The pilot area spans the two neighboring villages “9243 Jonschwil” and “9247 Henau” in eastern Switzerland, which are part of the SAK distribution grid. It involves a grid area with 419 different end consumers, including a mix of industrial demand response, multi-family buildings, and single-family houses. The area selected is characterized by a high penetration of PV infeed, EV charging, and heat pumps. The whole pilot area is supplied by three MV/LW transformers, which operate close to their capacity limit in certain days of the year.

Figure 2: Perimeter of the pilot area in Henau (left) and Jonschwil (right).

3. Project Outcomes so far & Outlook

ENFLATE is a four-year project (September 2022 to August 2026). Starting from fall 2024, there will be one full year of pilot operation with live market operation and physical DSF activation in the pilot households.

The activities conducted so far focused on the market design and the necessary software upgrades. A screenshot of the localflex platform is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the localflex platform, zoomed in on the Jonschwil pilot area

Dedicated communication tools were developed to engage and onboard the pilot inhabitants. Hardware for metering and switching the residential heat pumps, electric boilers and electromobility charging stations was installed in all households.

Through the demonstration activities it is expected the diminishment of the costs associated with market-based procurement of flexibility in comparison to alternatives approaches of flexibility activation (ripple control, time of use tariffs), the hosting capacity of the grid will be increased due to flexibility being used to avoid curtailment of renewable energy and the MV transformer lifespan will be improved due to improved utilization factor and reduced peak load.

This demonstration aims to minimize the barriers for the establishment of new business models for stakeholders in the energy services, and thus increases both active consumers' willingness to invest in RES and their quality of life. The business models developed in the project enable households to combine the provision of energy services focused on flexibility with investments in assets at consumer level that contribute to long-term changes in electricity production or consumption, such as RES generation, deep renovations, new, more efficient and intelligent appliances that form a major part of household energy consumption (e.g., heating).

Beyond the ENFLATE project, it is envisioned that building upon the activities of the project more and more stakeholders in the European region will start creating new business models that combine services across different industries, with an explicit focus on the end-users' prosperity.

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References

- [1] ENFLATE consortium website, <https://enflate.eu/>, Last accessed 2024-05-01.